

The holy Niels of Århus (younger text)

By Svend Clausen, TBC

Entry tags: Miracle tales, Christianity, Religious Group, Catholic, Latin Text, Text, Hagiography, Catholic text

The holy Niels of Århus was a local Danish saint venerated in Århus diocese in Jutland during the middle ages. Two hagiographic texts are known about him: an older one and a younger one. Even though these two have been preserved together as part of a collective manuscript, it is necessary to distinguish between them as they are quite different not only in dating and in their individual background of creation, but also stylistically. As the dating of the younger Niels legend has been revised for the purpose of this description, it is necessary to shortly explain why. The only dating of the younger legend known for sure so far is that it must have been written after 1306. Hans Olrik therefore suggested that it was written probably some time into the 14th C. and suggested that the deacon Trugot of Århus mentioned in the legend as a contemporary person could very well be the same man as the canon Trugot of Århus known in 1345 from an external source. Later on M.Cl. Gertz repeated this observation and suggested furthermore that the writer of the younger text probably lived around c. 1350. Backing this up he identified also another man mentioned in the text as a contemporary person: cantor Johannes of Århus. Gertz identified that this cantor Johannes (the latin form of the Danish name Jens) was also mentioned in 1345 in an external source. However, it seems possible to specify the dating of the younger text a little more and place it a bit earlier. Going over the preserved medieval documents, one cantor Jens Rød of Århus (i.e. Johannes) is mentioned for the first time on 12. November 1335. His presumed predecessor as cantor, Jakob, is mentioned for the last time on 15. Oktober 1325. This cantor Jens of Århus is mentioned for the last time on 9. May 1345. His presumed successor in office, prior Peder, is mentioned for the first time as cantor in a document dated in 1354 before 14. april. Since the younger text about the holy Niels was written while Johannes (Jens) was cantor of Århus, it thus must have been written sometime after 15. Oktober 1325, but before 14. April 1354. Such a dating can likely be narrowed down even further, though, as Hans Olrik's abovementioned suggestion seems highly likely. The deacon Trugot of Århus mentioned in the legend as a contemporary person must be presumed to be the same man as the canon Trugot of Århus known in 1345. This particular name, Trugot, does not seem to have been common enough in Denmark during that era to expect it as highly probable that two persons of that same name were very likely to have been in office in Århus diocese at the same time. The fact that the younger holy Niels text describes deacon Trugot as a contemporary man who studied in Paris at the time of writing is thus probably decisive. Since Trugot had become a canon by 1345, the younger holy Niels text was probably written before 1345 while he was only still a deacon. His studies in Paris, as well as his later advancement as canon, is thus most likely explained by yet another preserved document from 29.3.1345 stating that Århus diocese had a rule demanding that all newly elected canons of Århus diocese had to study for 2 years at a university before they could receive the benefits of any of the estates belonging to the holy chapter of Århus diocese. The university studies of deacon Trugot in Paris thus probably took place at some point before 1345 so that he was able to advance and become canon, when he came back to Denmark, and subsequently also receive the estates attached to the position. All in all, the younger text about the holy Niels of Århus, was therefore probably written after 15. Oktober 1325 (the last mention of cantor Jakob), but before c. 1345 when Trugot is known to have advanced and become a canon. As for the text itself, the younger saint's legend about the holy Niels of Århus does not follow the normal somewhat stricter structure of hagiography. It is a structurally loose collection of anecdotes from his life and miracle stories from after his death. The sources of the writer for his text seem to have been twofold: some parts of the text he copied from a long lost manuscript in Danish which he found in the rectory of the still preserved Skejby village church in Århus diocese. These parts he then must have translated from Danish into latin. Other parts of the younger holy Niels text are much more likely to have been based on the recollections of senior members of the holy chapter and older clergymen in office at Århus diocese. The

younger text is thus not a classic hagiographic text as much as it is composite collection of anecdotes and miracle stories deemed worthy of remembrance by the author. As for the holy Niels himself, he was a Danish prince who died in 1180. He was of royal blood as son of king Knud III of Denmark, who had been murdered by the henchmen of a rival king during a civil war in 1157. Niels appears in a few contemporary documents, but other than that not much is known about his life apart from what is told in the two preserved texts about him.

Date Range: 1325 CE - 1345 CE

Region: Århus diocese

Region tags: Denmark

Map very roughly showing the borders of Århus diocese in Denmark during the 14th C. when the text about the holy Niels was written here.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: M. Cl. Gertz: *Vitae Sanctorum Danorum*, København, 1908-1912

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Nicolaus_Arhusiensis
(background information about the two texts about the holy Niels)

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The lost Danish manuscript was stored in the rectory of Skejby village church within Århus diocese. The original behind the preserved latin manuscript was probably stored in the diocesan library or archive of Århus.

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Paper (nowadays), originally probably parchment

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: The original parchment must have been prepared

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: It was partially copied (from a now long lost manuscript in Danish) and also translated into latin by an anonymous clergyman from Århus diocese

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Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

- No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

- No

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

- Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

- Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

- No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

- No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The answer is perhaps both yes and no at the same time. The holy Niels was venerated in Århus diocese in the medieval period, and even though the younger text about Niels was not necessarily considered to be the official hagiographic text about him, it is likely to have been read and used somehow in the veneration within the diocese nonetheless.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

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Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

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Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that the miracle stories are moralistic

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: The lost manuscript in Danish seems likely to have been used in the village church somehow, but the preserved latin manuscript is more likely to have been used in the diocese.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– No

↳ Content of text?

– No

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: The writer does not necessarily seem to view the lost Danish manuscript as an improper version, but he probably needed to translate it into latin in order to be able to use it amongst all the other latin texts in the diocese.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Naming witnesses and sources etc.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: The writer adds to the canon about the holy Niels by copying and translating the Danish manuscript and by adding miracle stories from the diocese

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: The two texts are preserved as a single manuscript

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No

↳ Optimism/hope
– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Notes: It tells about how Niels was so good that he bought birds from the hunters to let them fly away into freedom.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: hagiography

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: hagiography

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that holy Niels was venerated on a specific date.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: It tells about how a cross should be put on the hill where the body of holy Niels was lying before it was to be carried to Århus

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

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Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

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Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

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Non-human supernatural beings are present

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– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Maintenance of space does appear in the story where the cross at Holy Niels's hill is to be replaced for a new one.

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

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Notes: hagiography

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– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that holy Niels was venerated on a specific date.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

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Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

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Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that the miracle stories are moralistic

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

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Notes: It tells about how Niels was so good that he bought birds from the hunters to let them fly away into freedom.

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Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

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Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

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Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Maintenance of space does appear in the story where the cross at Holy Niels's hill is to be replaced for a new one.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The holy chapter of Århus diocese

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Although there is a miracle a story about a boy stealing apples

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: the holy chapter of Århus probably

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the deacon Thrugot's studies at the university of Paris are mentioned

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None of the above

– Other

Notes: None of the above

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

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Notes: The holy chapter of Århus diocese

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Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: Although there is a miracle a story about a boy stealing apples

Bibliography

General References

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